

ISic0030

I.Sicily inscription 0030

Language

Latin

Type

votive (?)

Material

limestone

Object**Editor**

Jonathan Prag

Principal Contributor

Jonathan Prag

Contributors

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Autopsy

No Autopsy

Last Change

2020-11-26 - Simona Stoyanova restructured bibliography

Place of origin (ancient)

Panhormus

Place of origin (modern)

Palermo

Provenance**Coordinates****Current Location**

Italy, Sicily, Palermo, Museo Archeologico

Physical Description

Dimensions

Height cm

Width cm

Depth cm

Layout

Execution

Engraved

Letter Forms

Letter heights:

Line 1: mm

Interlineation

Interlineation line 1 to 2: mm

Text

1. [---]Hostilianus

2. p(ecunia) · s(ua) p(osuit)

3. d(edit) d(edicavit)

Apparatus

Text of

Translation (en)

Hostilianus erected, gave, and dedicated (this monument) at his own expense.

Commentary

Digital identifiers:

TM 491795

EDR 137836

EDCS 22000879

Bibliography

Mommsen, Th. 1883. Inscriptiones Bruttiorum Lucaniae Campaniae Siciliae Sardiniae Latinae. Pars posterior. Inscriptiones Siciliae et Sardiniae. *Corpus Inscriptionum Latinarum, consilio et auctoritate Academiae Litterarum Regiae Borussicae editum*. Berlin. At 10.7293 (<http://arachne.uni-koeln.de/item/buchseite/650791>)

Bivona, L. 1970. Iscrizioni latine lapidarie del Museo di Palermo. *Sikelia*. Palermo. At 30

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Cite as:

J. Prag et al. (2020-12-17): ISic0030. <http://sicily.classics.ox.ac.uk>. (Collection: TEI edition). <http://doi.org/10.5281/zenodo.4333836>